

SYLYBUM MARIANUM (L.) GAERTN. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PLANT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14030935>

Abstract. *This species, known as olaot, has been used in folk medicine for more than 2000 years as a medicinal plant against liver, kidney, rheumatism, gastrointestinal and heart diseases. In modern medicine, it is also widely used as a protective agent against biological and chemical poisoning. This article provides information on the chemical composition of the medicinal plant, its importance in folk medicine and modern medicine, and the use of medicines prepared from its various organs.*

Keywords: *silybum marianum, herb, medicinal, medicine, silymarin, disease, flower, leaf, fruit.*

INTRODUCTION. It is important to suggest that milk thistle is a medicinal plant that has been used for many years as a remedy for various diseases. The main component of the *S. marianum* fruit extract (silymarin) is the flavonolignan silybin, which is not only the main element of silymarin, but also the most active ingredient of this extract, as confirmed in various studies. This compound belongs to a group of flavonoids known as flavonolignans. The structure of silybin consists of two main units. The first is based on tachyfolin, the second - on the phenylpropanoid link. Since the 1970s, the substance silybin, isolated from the seeds of *S. marianum*, has been included in official medicine as a substance with hepatoprotective properties. There are many studies reflecting the chemical properties of olaote, but there is insufficient scientific information on its molecular structure, metabolism and use in folk medicine. Therefore, we set ourselves the task of studying information on the use of oleander in folk, modern medicine and pharmaceuticals.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS. *Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn, known as olaot and used in folk medicine for over 2000 years as a medicinal plant against the liver, kidneys, rheumatism, gastrointestinal diseases, heart diseases and bile [1]. In Europe, its leaves are traditionally added to various salads, and the seeds are used by nursing mothers as a stimulant [2]. In Iran, the medicinal plant *S. marianum* is used as a protective agent for biological poisoning caused by various mycotoxins, snake venom and bacterial toxins, as well as for chemical poisoning with heavy metals, fluorides, pesticides, cardiotoxic, neurotoxic, hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic substances [3]. Many studies have shown that silymarin, found in its various organs, significantly reduces lipid peroxidation and has antioxidant, antihypertensive, antidiabetic and hepatoprotective effects [4, 5]. In addition, *S. marianum* was found to reduce the viability, adhesion and migration of tumor cells due to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). The main component of *S. marianum* extract is silymarin, its amount is 70-80% in the leaves, seeds and fruits of the plant. Silybin, isosilybin, silychristin, isosilychristin, tachyfolin, apigenin and silydianin were also found in this plant. The remaining 20-30% is represented by a relatively undefined polymeric fraction of flavonoids [6]. The substance silybin is the main component of silymarin, which has a very effective healing effect compared to other flavonolignans [7].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION. This is a biennial plant belonging to the Asteraceae family. Its height reaches 30-60 cm. The stem is strong, erect, sparsely branched, linear, smooth or with slightly cobwebby hairs formed in the second year.

Definitely, the leaves of the rhizome are large (length up to 40-80 cm and width up to 15-30 cm), oblong-oval, strongly wrinkled. The leaves on the stem are arranged alternately. The leaf blades are shiny with transverse stripes, covered with yellowish spines along the edges and veins below.

The flowers are predominantly pink or purple. In some cases, it can be red. The flowers are collected in one spherical basket with a large opening. The tip of the leaves around the flower is prickly. All the flowers in the oleander basket are tubular, bisexual. The fruit consists of pistachios. The upper part is smooth, sometimes wrinkled, reaches 5-6 mm in length. Flowers in the basket bloom in May and August, depending on the climate. The fruits ripen in September and October. Due to the fact that the inflorescences of the plant bloom at different times, the ripening of the fruits will not be massive. Therefore, it is necessary to take this process into account when collecting fruits.

Besides that, *S. marianum* is widespread in Western and Central Europe (Germany, Poland, Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Austria, Switzerland, Holland, Belgium, England, France, Portugal), southern regions of Russia and Ukraine, Western Siberia, as well as in America and Asia. It also includes the Karakum, Syrdarya, Pamir-Aloi, Caucasus regions of Central Asia. This plant is also widespread in the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, which are the southern regions of our country. This species grows in the Jizzakh, Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions of our country mainly along the banks of ditches, roadsides, grain fields and fields planted with various agricultural crops. In the flora of Uzbekistan (Flora of Uzbekistan, v. 6, p. 382) it is noted that the distribution of *S. marianum* species is widespread only in the Surkhandarya region of our republic.

According to B.A. Nigmatullaev (2018), this species is currently an invasive plant species that has spread to neighboring territories, occupying large areas and forming many new populations.

Ripe dried fruits, leaves, seeds and roots are collected from the plant for medicinal purposes. Seeds are collected in August-September. The harvesting process is carried out when the wrapping leaves of the baskets dry out. It is advisable to organize the collection work early in the morning. At this time, the flowers of the plant will not open. The collected flowers are dried in a place protected from sunlight, and the raw materials can be stored in well-ventilated warehouses throughout the year. The roots are extracted in the fall. The extracted roots are washed and dried in a sunny place. The roots can be dried in special drying equipment at a temperature of 40-50°C.

Chemical composition. The main active substance found in the plant is silymarin, a biologically active substance that is very rare in nature. Silymarin is a complex substance consisting of a mixture of three isomers - silybin, silydianin and silychristin.

In addition, more than 30-35% of oils and 0.1% of essential oils, biogenic amines such as tyramine, histamine and resins were found in the composition of oleander fruits. At the same time, macroelements (K-9.2 mg / g, Ca-16.6 mg / g, Mg-4.2 mg / g, Fe-0.08 mg / g), microelements (B-22.4 µg / g, J-0.09 µg / g), Mn-0.1 µg / g, Cu-1.16 µg / g, Se-22.9 µg / g, Cr-0.15 µg / g, Zn- 0.71 µg / g, etc.) and vitamins A, D, E, K and B were also found. Application in medicine. Oleander preparations enhance the liver's detoxification function, promote liver tissue restoration, increase

bile secretion, improve fat digestion, have a diuretic, anti-inflammatory, wound-healing effect, an ointment against various wounds, capillary vessels, have strengthening and antioxidant properties. Olaota seed oil has healing, anti-burn, hepatoprotective properties. In terms of biological activity, they are not inferior to retail oil. Fenugreek seeds are effective in the treatment of chronic hepatitis, liver cirrhosis and toxic-metabolic lesions (alcoholic, medicinal, chemical, food), toxicosis during pregnancy, cholecystitis, inflammation of the gallbladder and cholelithiasis. Also, when salt accumulates in the spleen, thyroid gland, joints, varicose veins, diabetes, narrowing of the vascular walls (atherosclerosis), when eliminating various edemas, obesity, radiculitis. It is used for joint pain, hemorrhoids and allergic diseases.

The use of crushed oleander seed pods accelerates the secretory activity of the gastrointestinal tract, the functions of contraction and relaxation. At the same time, the use of this powder promotes the complete absorption of fats and fat-soluble vitamins, relieves constipation, eliminates inflammatory diseases of the gastric mucosa and colon. Oleander seeds are used for preventive purposes after chemotherapy and light therapy for tumor diseases. It is also widely used to eliminate intoxication caused by excessive alcohol consumption. A decoction prepared from the root is taken as a diuretic for diarrhea, radiculitis and vascular spasms. The juice of the leaves of Olaot is drunk for constipation, inflammation of the mucous membrane of the colon and stomach, joint pain. A decoction of the oleander root is also used as a preventive and therapeutic agent for toothache, gingivitis, stomatitis, pharyngitis. Tincture and tincture prepared from the seeds are also used to eliminate varicose veins caused by dilation of the veins and blood vessels. A decoction and powder of seeds and porridge from fresh leaves are used for open fractures, wounds, various burns, prevention of purulent processes, treatment of rashes. Fenugreek seed oil is also used in the treatment of acne, psoriasis, hair loss, acne, eczema, hyperkeratosis and neurodermatitis.

According to O.K.Khozhimatov (2021), experimental and clinical studies have confirmed the effective therapeutic effect of tincture and other preparations of oleander fruits in chronic cholecystopathy and posthepatitis syndrome. The preparations "Silibor" and "Silimar" are prepared from the fruits in the form of tablets. Analogous drugs are also produced from olaot. For example; These include Bulgaria (Karsil), Russia (Silibinin) and Germany (Legalon). Methods of using a medicinal plant. Ripe seeds of the plant are dried, ground in a special device (coffee grinder) and turned into powder. The powder is drunk three times a day half an hour before meals, one teaspoon at a time. It is recommended to chew the prepared powder directly or wash it down with water. The course of treatment with seed powder is one month. In some cases, the course can be repeated after a ten-day break. If necessary and depending on the patient's condition, this drug can be taken for 2 or 3 months. A one- or two-time course is recommended as a preventive measure to cleanse and restore the liver in case of excessive alcohol consumption. To do this, 30 g of ground seeds are thoroughly boiled in 0.5 l of water over medium heat until the volume is reduced by half. The finished decoction is left for 10 minutes and filtered through a three-layer gauze. This decoction is drunk one tablespoon every hour or one hour after meals 3 times a day. To prepare a decoction of oleander roots, add one tablespoon of dried and crushed root material to 250 ml of boiling water and mix well. This mixture is boiled in a closed container in a water bath for half an hour. The finished decoction is filtered through a two-layer gauze. If the initial volume of this decoction decreases, add water boiled to the original volume (250 ml). This decoction is drunk 3 times a day, one tablespoon before meals. To one liter of juice obtained by squeezing freshly cut leaves, add 50 ml of 70% ethyl alcohol. Store the mixture in the refrigerator. This mixture is drunk

half an hour before meals twice a day for 30 days to treat liver diseases, improve the gastrointestinal tract, and eliminate atherosclerosis. To 0.5 liters of any vegetable oil, add five teaspoons of fenugreek seeds and boil this mixture in a water bath for ten minutes, during which time the oil contained in the seeds goes into solution. Pass this mixture through a sieve with small holes and store in the refrigerator. This mixture is applied externally in the form of an ointment to treat various wounds, purulent wounds, burns, skin diseases. You can also use an oleander leaf to eliminate the above skin diseases. To do this, the leaves with the thorns removed are homogenized using a homogenizer or mortar until a homogeneous mass of porridge is formed. This porridge wrapped in gauze is applied to wounds, scratches and cuts. If necessary, it is recommended to change this bandage every 2-3 days.

Although there are no contraindications or side effects to the use of this plant in folk medicine or modern medicine, you should consult a doctor before using it. It is not recommended to take medications and decoctions made from different parts of the plant during pregnancy. During treatment with this plant, you should not eat spicy, fatty foods or alcohol.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that at present time the number of medicines and food supplements prepared on the basis of the oleander plant is increasing all over the world. This means an expansion of the scale of scientific research on the chemical composition of this medicinal plant, its use in folk medicine and modern medicine, the technology of its cultivation based on organic farming to obtain environmentally friendly raw materials.

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